

**A NOVEL ADAPTIVE MOTH FLAME OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM FOR
GLOBAL NUMERICAL OPTIMIZATION**Naveen Sihag^{*1}

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^{*1}Department of Computer Engineering, Rajasthan Technical University Kota, Rajasthan 324002,
India**ABSTRACT**

A novel bio-inspired optimization algorithm based on the navigation strategy of Moths in universe called the Moth-Flame optimization (MFO) Algorithm in contrast to meta-heuristic, main feature is randomization having a relevant role in both exploration and exploitation in optimization problem. A novel randomization technique termed adaptive technique is integrated with MFO and exercised on unconstrained test benchmark function and localization of partial discharge in transformer like geometry. MFO algorithm has quality feature that it uses logarithmic spiral function so it covers a vast area in exploration phase then addition with powerful randomization adaptive technique potent the AMFO algorithm to attain global optimal solution and faster convergence with less parameter dependency. Adaptive MFO (AMFO) solutions are evaluated and results shows its competitively better performance over standard optimization algorithms.

Keywords:

Meta-heuristic; Moth-Flame optimizer; Adaptive technique; Global optimal; Navigation; Partial Discharge.

INTRODUCTION

A novel nature –inspired, Moth-Flame optimization algorithm [1] based on the navigation mechanism called transverse orientation of Moths in space. Transverse orientation for navigation uses a constant angle by Moths with respect to Moon as Moon is thousands of miles away from Moths so this mechanism guarantees for flying in straight direction. Moths applied this transverse mechanism for artificial lights that is more nearer to Moths in compare to Moon, then Moths are tricked as they do not keep fixed angle with respect to flame or angle is gradually decreasing so fly around flames in a Logarithmic spiral way and finally converges towards the flame. This Logarithmic spiral way represents the exploration area and it guarantees to exploit the optimum solution.

In the meta-heuristic algorithms, randomization play a very important role in both exploration and exploitation where more strengthen randomization techniques are Markov chains, Levy flights and Gaussian or normal distribution and new technique is adaptive technique. So meta-heuristic algorithms on integrated with adaptive technique results in less computational time to reach optimum solution, local minima avoidance and faster convergence.

In past, many optimization algorithms based on gradient search for solving linear and non-linear equation but in gradient search method value of objective function and constraint unstable and multiple peaks if problem having more than one local optimum.

Population based MFO is a meta-heuristic optimization algorithm has an ability to avoid local optima and get global optimal solution that make it appropriate for practical applications without structural modifications for solving different constrained or unconstrained optimization problems. MFO integrated with adaptive technique reduces the computational times for highly complex problems.

Paper under literature review are: Adaptive Cuckoo Search Algorithm (ACSA) [2] [3], QGA [4], Acoustic Partial discharge (PD) [5] [6], HGAPSO [7], PSACO [8], HSABA [9], PBILKH [10], KH-QPSO [11], IFA-HS [12], HS/FA [13], CKH [14], HS/BA [15], HPSACO [16], CSKH [17], HS-CSS [18], PSOHS [19], DEKH [20], HS/CS [21], HSBBO [22], CSS-PSO [23] etc.

Recently trend of optimization is to improve performance of meta-heuristic algorithms [24] by integrating with chaos theory, Levy flights strategy, Adaptive randomization technique, Evolutionary boundary handling scheme, and genetic operators like as crossover and mutation. Popular genetic operators used in KH [25] that

can accelerate its global convergence speed. Evolutionary constraint handling scheme is used in Interior Search Algorithm (ISA) [26] that avoid upper and lower limits of variables.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: The next Section describes the Moth-flame optimizer algorithm and its algebraic equations are given in Section 2. Section 3 includes description of Adaptive technique. Section 4 consists of simulation results of unconstrained benchmark test function, convergence curve and tables of results compared with source algorithm. In Section 5 PD localization by acoustic emission, in section 6 conclusion is drawn. Finally, acknowledgment gives regards detail and at the end, references are written.

MOTH-FLAME OPTIMIZER

Moth-Flame optimizer is first introduced by SeyedaliMirjalili in 2015 [1]. MFO is a population based algorithm; we represent the set of moths in a matrix:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} m_{1,1} & m_{1,2} & \dots & m_{1,d} \\ m_{2,1} & m_{2,2} & \dots & m_{2,d} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{n,1} & m_{n,2} & \dots & m_{n,d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where n represents number of moths and d represents number of variables (dimension).

For all the moths, we also assume that there is an array for storing the corresponding fitness values as follows:

$$OM = \begin{bmatrix} OM_1 \\ OM_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ OM_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where n is the number of moths.

Note that the fitness value is the return value of the fitness (objective) function for each moth. The position vector (first row in the matrix M for instance) of each moth is passed to the fitness function and the output of the fitness function is assigned to the corresponding moth as its fitness function (OM_i in the matrix OM for instance).

Other key components in the proposed algorithm are flames. We consider a matrix similar to the moth matrix:

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} FL_{1,1} & FL_{1,2} & \cdot & \cdot & FL_{1,d} \\ FL_{2,1} & FL_{2,2} & \cdot & \cdot & FL_{2,d} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ FL_{n,1} & FL_{n,2} & \cdot & \cdot & FL_{n,d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where n shows number of moths and d represents number of variables (dimension).

We know that the dimension of M and F arrays are equal. For the flames, we also assume that there is an array for storing the corresponding fitness values:

$$OF = \begin{bmatrix} OFL_1 \\ OFL_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ OFL_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Where n is the number of moths.

Here, it should be noted that moths and flames both are solutions. The difference between them is the way we treat and update them, in iteration. The moths are actual search agents that move around the search space, whereas flames are the best position of moths that obtains so far. Therefore, each moth searches around a flame and updates it in case of finding a better solution. With this mechanism, a moth never loses its best solution.

The MFO algorithm is three-rows that approximate the global solution of the problems defined like as follows:

$$MFO = (I, P, T) \quad (5)$$

I is the function that yield an uncertain population of moths and corresponding fitness values.

The methodical model of this function is as follows:

$$I: \phi \rightarrow \{M, OM\} \quad (6)$$

The P function, which is the main function, expresses the moths around the search space. This function receives the matrix of M and takes back its updated one at every time with each iteration.

$$P: M \rightarrow M \quad (7)$$

The T returns true and false according to the termination Criterion satisfaction:

$$T: M \rightarrow \{true, false\} \quad (8)$$

In order to mathematical model this behavior, we change the position of each Moth with respect to a flame using the following equation:

$$M_i = S(M_i, F_j) \quad (9)$$

Where M_i indicate the i^{th} moth, F_j indicates the j^{th} flame, and S is the spiral function.

Considering these points, we define a log (logarithmic scale) spiral for the MFO algorithm as follows:

$$S(M_i, F_j) = D_i * e^{bt} \cos(2\pi t) + F_j \quad (10)$$

Where: D_i expresses the distance of the moth for the j^{th} flame, b is a constant for expressing the shape of the log (logarithmic) spiral, and t is a random value in $[-1, 1]$.

$$D_i = |F_j - M_i| \quad (11)$$

Where: M_i indicate the i^{th} moth, F_j indicates the j^{th} flame, and where D_i expresses the path length of the i^{th} moth for the j^{th} flame.

The number of flames is adaptively decreased over the course of iterations. We use the following formula:

$$flame\ no = round\left(N - l * \frac{N-1}{T}\right) \quad (12)$$

Where l is the current number of iteration, N is the maximum number of flames, and T indicates the maximum number of iterations.

Fig. 1: A conceptual model of position updating of a moth around a flame

We utilize Quicksort algorithm, the sort is of $O(n \log n)$ in the best and $O(n^2)$ in the worst condition, respectively. Considering the P function, so, total computational complexity is defined as follows:

$$O(MFO) = O(t(O(\text{Quick sort}) + O(\text{position update})))$$

$$O(MFO) = O(t(n^2 + n * d)) = O(tn^2 + tnd)$$

(13)

Where n shows number of moths, t represents maximum number of iterations, and d represents number of variables.

ADAPTIVE MFO

In the meta-heuristic algorithms, randomization play a very important role in both exploration and exploitation where more randomization techniques are Markov chains, Levy flights and Gaussian or normal distribution and new technique is adaptive technique. Adaptive technique used by Pauline Ong in Cuckoo Search Algorithm (CSA) [2] and shows improvement in results of CSA algorithms. The Adaptive technique [3] includes best features like it consists of less parameter dependency, not required to define initial parameter and step size or position towards optimum solution is adaptively changes according to its functional fitness value over the course of iteration. So meta-heuristic algorithms on integrated with adaptive technique results in less computational time to reach optimum solution, local minima avoidance and faster convergence.

$$X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + randn * \left(\frac{1}{t}\right)^{\left|\frac{(bestf(t) - fi(t))}{(bestf(t) - worstf(t))}\right|} \quad (14)$$

Where X_i^{t+1} new solution of i -th dimension in t -th iteration $f(t)$ is the fitness value

Simulation Results for Unconstraint Test Benchmark Function

Table 1: Benchmark Test functions

No.	Name	Function	Dim	Range	Fmin
F1	Sphere	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 * R(x)$	10	[-100, 100]	0
F2	Schwefel 2.22	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \prod_{i=1}^n x_i * R(x)$	10	[-10, 10]	0
F3	Schwefel 1.2	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^i x_j \right)^2 * R(x)$	10	[-100, 100]	0
F4	Schwefel 2.21	$f(x) = \max_i \{ x_i , 1 \leq i \leq n\}$	10	[-100, 100]	0
F5	Rosenbrock's Function	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left[100(x_{i+1} - x_i^2)^2 + (x_i - 1)^2 \right] * R(x)$	10	[-30, 30]	0
F6	Step Function	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n ([x_i + 0.5])^2 * R(x)$	10	[-100, 100]	0
F7	Quartic Function	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n i x_i^4 + random[0,1] * R(x)$	10	[-1.28, 1.28]	0
F8	Schwefel 2.26	$F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n -x_i \sin(\sqrt{ x_i }) * R(x)$	10	[-500, 500]	(-418.9829*5)

F9	Rastrigin	$F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n [x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i) + 10] * R(x)$	10	[-5.12, 5.12]	0
F10	Ackley's Function	$F(x) = -20 \exp \left(-0.2 \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2} \right) - \exp \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(2\pi x_i) \right) + 20 + e * R(x)$	10	[-32, 32]	0
F11	Griewank Function	$F(x) = \frac{1}{4000} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \prod_{i=1}^n \cos \left(\frac{x_i}{\sqrt{i}} \right) + 1 * R(x)$	10	[-600, 600]	0
F12	Penalty 1	$F(x) = \frac{\pi}{n} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10 \sin(\pi y_1) + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (y_i - 1)^2 \\ [1 + 10 \sin^2(\pi y_{i+1})] + (y_n - 1)^2 \end{array} \right\}$ $y_i = 1 + \frac{x_i + 1}{4},$ $u(x_i, a, k, m) = \begin{cases} k(x_i - a)^m & x_i > a \\ 0 & -a < x_i < a \\ k(-x_i - a)^m & x_i < -a \end{cases}$	10	[-50, 50]	0
F13	Penalty 2	$F(x) = 0.1 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sin^2(3\pi x_1) + \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - 1)^2 \\ [1 + \sin^2(3\pi x_i + 1)] \\ + (x_n - 1)^2 [1 + \sin^2(2\pi x_n)] \end{array} \right\}$ $+ \sum_{i=1}^n u(x_i, 5, 100, 4) * R(x)$	10	[-50, 50]	0

F14	De Jounge (Shekel's Foxholes)	$F(x) = \left(\frac{1}{500} + \sum_{j=1}^{25} \frac{1}{j + \sum_{i=1}^2 (x_i - a_{ij})^6} \right)^{-1}$	2	[-1, 1]	65.536, 65.536]
F15	Kowalik's Function	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{11} a_i - \left[\frac{x_i (b_i^2 + b_i x_2)}{b_i^2 + b_i x_3 + x_4} \right]^2$	4	[-5,5]	0.0003 0
F16	Cube function	$f(x) = 100(x_2 - x_1^3)^2 + (1 - x_1)^2$	30	[-100, 100]	0
F17	Matyas function	$f(x) = 0.26(x_1^2 + x_2^2) - 0.48x_1x_2$	30	[-30, 30]	0
F18	Powell function	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{D-2} \left\{ (x_{i-1} + 10x_i)^2 + 5(x_{i+1} - x_{i+2})^2 + (x_i - 2x_{i+1})^4 + 10(x_{i-1} - x_{i+2})^4 \right\}$	4	[-30, 30]	0
F19	Beale Function	$f(x) = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &(1.5 - x_1 + x_1x_2)^2 + (2.25 - x_1 + x_1x_2^2)^2 \\ &+ (2.625 - x_1 + x_1x_2^3)^2 \end{aligned} \right\}$	30	[-100, 100]	0
F20	levy13 function	$f(x) = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\sin^2(3\pi x_1) + (x_1 - 1)^2 (1 + \sin^2(3\pi x_2)) \\ &+ (x_2 - 1)^2 (1 + \sin^2(2\pi x_2)) \end{aligned} \right\}$	30	[-10, 10]	0

Table 2: Internal Parameters

Parameter Name	Search Agents no.	Max. Iteration no.	No. of Evolution
F1-F16, F18, F20	30	500	20-30
F17	30	100	20-30
F19	30	300	20-30
Acoustic PD Localization	40	200	20
Note:- Scale specified on axis, Not specified means axis are linear scale			

F_1

F_2

F_3

F_4

F_5

F_6

F_{13}

F_{14}

F_{15}

F_{16}

F_{17}

F_{18}

Fig. 2: Convergence Curve of Benchmark Test Function

Table 3: Result for benchmark functions

Function.	Moth-Flame optimizer (MFO)			Adaptive Moth-Flame Optimizer (AMFO)		
	Ave	Best	S.D.	Ave	Best	S.D.
F1	5.043E-14	4.9088E-14	1.897E-15	4.9015E-13	1.8855E-14	1.8975E-15
F2	5	5.8126E-09	7.0711	3.8783E-09	1.9674E-09	7.0711
F3	0.12535	0.016445	0.15401	0.021517	0.002442	0.15401
F4	0.53694	0.056767	0.67906	0.068018	0.047005	0.67906
F5	80.5512	7.4857	103.3302	11.8256	1.4594	103.3302
F6	4.0197E-13	1.6146E-13	3.4013E-13	4.4177E-14	6.0356E-15	3.4013E-13
F7	0.016558	0.0063498	0.014437	0.013578	0.0034856	0.014437
F8	-3210.4316	-3479.1989	380.0943	-3833.7553	-3952.9522	380.0943
F9	22.3865	14.9244	10.5531	13.9294	11.9395	10.5531
F10	0.82311	3.5568E-07	1.1641	1.4354E-07	9.3408E-08	1.1641
F11	0.15008	0.14755	0.0035761	0.16858	0.12538	0.0035761
F12	1.3484E-13	8.2781E-14	7.3624E-14	0.1555	3.7085E-14	7.3624E-14
F13	0.0054937	1.5795E-13	0.0077692	3.3181E-14	3.0611E-14	0.0077692
F14	0.00077827	0.0007738	6.3267E-06	0.00071284	0.00067665	6.3267E-06
F15	-2.6567	-2.6829	0.037044	-6.418	-10.1532	0.037044

F16	1.6086	0.061081	2.1886	0.00039161	1.034E-07	2.1886
F17	5.8946E-52	1.0619E-54	8.3211E-52	1.2535E-25	1.06628E-62	1.7727E-25
F18	1.5717E-05	1.3193E-05	3.5703E-06	1.4327E-05	3.6142E-07	3.5703E-06
F19	1.482E-07	1.9613E-11	2.0956E-07	4.9189E-12	3.1077E-21	2.0956E-16
F20	1.4253E-18	4.5623E-19	1.3705E-18	5.4212E-19	2.2389E-20	7.3501E-19

ACOUSTIC PD LOCALIZATION SENSOR POSITION

Dielectric breakdown in transformers is most frequently initiated by partial discharges. The consequences of these types of occurrences can be hazardous if not detected in a timely fashion. Regular PD analysis gives an accurate indication of the status of the deterioration process. So it is possible to foretell developing fault condition by online monitoring and precautionary tests. It is very much essential to have information of PD level and location to plan maintenance of electrical equipment. A famous method of understanding the health of the transformer is by studying the partial discharge signals. Monitoring of transformer can be either online or offline. The primary established techniques for electrical PD detection by measuring current or Radio Frequency (RF) pulses. Suppression of interference is one of the main challenges in detecting PDs, either while the transformer is off-line or on-line in a noisy environment. The off-line PD detection methods only provide snapshots in time of part of the transformer's condition. On the other hand, no standards have yet been developed for on-line electrical monitoring of PDs.

It is well known that the occurrence of discharge results in discharge current or voltage pulse, electromagnetic impulse radiation, ultrasonic impulse radiation and visible or ultraviolet light emission. Accordingly, there are several detection methods that have been developed to measure those phenomena respectively. Acoustic detection is one of them which is very famous nowadays.

PD generates acoustic waves in range of 20 kHz to 1 MHz. External system and internal system are two categories of acoustic detection techniques based on sensor location in transformer. External system is widely accepted as sensors are mounted outside of the transformer. An obvious advantage of the acoustic method is that it can locate the site of a PD by algorithms. Electromagnetic interference may cause corruption of signals captured by piezoelectric sensors.

A main objective is to determine the position of the PD source based on signals captured by sensor array inside the transformer tank as shown in Fig. 3. Each sensor will capture acoustic signals at different time as shown in Fig. 4. Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) algorithm has been implemented to find location of partial discharge source.

PDE equation in homogeneous medium for propagation of acoustic wave:

$$\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial t^2} = v^2 \nabla^2 P = v^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (15)$$

Where: $P(x, y, z, t)$ pressure wave field; function of space and time; x, y, z Cartesian coordinates (mm) and v acoustic wave velocity

(m/s).

Fig. 3: Visualization of PD source and sensor arrangement

Fig. 4: Schematic of acoustic time differences in reference to electrical PD signal

Table 4: Transformer dimension and Co-ordination position of sensor

Element	X-axis (mm)	Y-axis (mm)	Z-axis (mm)
Transformer Dimension	5000	3000	4000
Actual PD source	4500	2600	3700
Sensor (S ₁)	2500	0	2000
Sensor (S ₂)	2500	1500	4000
Sensor (S ₃)	5000	1500	2000
Sensor (S ₄)	2500	3000	2000
Sensor (S ₅)	0	1500	2000
<i>t₁=2600 micro-seconds (Reference)</i>			

$\tau_{i1} (\mu s) = [1600, 1500, 1900, 3524.69] - t_1, i = 2, 3, 4, 5$, And sensor 1 is assumed as reference paper [6].

Problem Formulation:

$$\tau_{21} = -1000 \times 10^{-03}, \tau_{31} = -1100 \times 10^{-03}, \quad (16)$$

$$\tau_{41} = -700 \times 10^{-03}, \tau_{51} = -924.69 \times 10^{-03},$$

$$P = \left[(x - x_1)^2 + (y - y_1)^2 + (z - z_1)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad (17)$$

$$a = \left[(x - x_2)^2 + (y - y_2)^2 + (z - z_2)^2 \right]^{0.5} - P - v_e \tau_{21}; \quad (18)$$

$$b = \left[(x - x_3)^2 + (y - y_3)^2 + (z - z_3)^2 \right]^{0.5} - P - v_e \tau_{31}; \quad (19)$$

$$c = \left[(x - x_4)^2 + (y - y_4)^2 + (z - z_4)^2 \right]^{0.5} - P - v_e \tau_{41}; \quad (20)$$

$$d = \left[(x - x_5)^2 + (y - y_5)^2 + (z - z_5)^2 \right]^{0.5} - P - v_e \tau_{51}; \quad (21)$$

$$\text{Min } \{D_f(x, y, z, v_e)\} = a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + d^2; \quad (22)$$

Subjected to

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 0 \leq x \leq x_{\max} \\ 0 \leq y \leq y_{\max} \\ 0 \leq z \leq z_{\max} \\ 1200 \leq v_e \leq 1500, \quad (m/s) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (23)$$

Where:

$x_{\max}, y_{\max}, z_{\max}$ and v_e are transformer tank dimension and equality sound velocity.

Calculated *PD* source is $P_c(x_c, y_c, z_c)$ comprehensive distance error of it with actual *PD* source $P(x, y, z)$ is

$$\Delta R = \left[(x - x_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2 + (z - z_c)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad (24)$$

Error of each co-ordinate is formulated:

$$\epsilon_r = \left| \frac{L_{act} - L_{cal}}{L_{act}} \right| \times 100\% \quad (25)$$

Maximum deviation $D_{\max}$

$$D_{\max} = \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &|x_{act} - x_{cal}| \\ &|y_{act} - y_{cal}| \\ &|z_{act} - z_{cal}| \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (26)$$

Where ; $L_{act}, x_{act}, y_{act}, z_{act}$ and $L_{cal}, x_{cal}, y_{cal}, z_{cal}$ actual and calculated co-ordinates respectively.

Table 5: Comparison of the results of PD localization

Coordinate (mm)	Actual PD source	MFO	AMFO	GA [4]
x	4500	4381.7521	4381.7725	4223.76
y	2600	2469.6056	2469.6147	2391.71
z	3700	3647.496	3647.5201	3503.04

Table 6: Error analysis

Error	MFO	AMFO	GA
Error of x%	2.627	2.627	6.14
Error of y%	5.015	5.014	8.01
Error of z%	1.419	1.418	5.32
D _{max} /mm	130.3944	130.3853	276.24
Comprehensive Error(ΔR /mm)	183.6897	183.6633	398.10

CONCLUSION

Moth-Flame Optimizer have an ability to find out optimum solution with constrained handling which includes both equality and inequality constraints. While obtaining optimum solution constraint limits should not be violated. Randomization plays an important role in both exploration and exploitation. Adaptive technique causes faster convergence, randomness, and stochastic behavior for improving solutions. Adaptive technique also used for random walk in search space when no neighboring solution exists to converse towards optimal solution. Acoustic PD source localization method based on AMFO algorithm is feasible. PD localization by AMFO gives better result than MFO algorithm and also accurate in compare to GA. The AMFO result of various unconstrained problems proves that it is also an effective method in solving challenging problems with unknown search space.

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